

Synthesis and structural evaluation of transition metal complexes of thiosemicarbazone and semicarbazone derived from pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde

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Abstract : This paper presents the synthesis and characterization of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of thiosemicarbazone (L^1) and semicarbazone (L^2) derived from pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde. All the complexes reported here had been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO correspond to non electrolytic nature. All the complexes are of high-spin type. On the basis of spectral studies various six coordinated geometry may be assigned for all the complexes except $\text{Co}(L)_2(\text{SO}_4)$ and $\text{Cu}(L)_2(\text{SO}_4)$ [where $L = L^1$ and L^2] which are of five coordinated square pyramidal geometry.

Keywords : Thiosemicarbazone, transition metal complex, pyrrole, semicarbazone.

Introduction

Interest in metal complexes with thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones ligands has been stimulated because biological activity is often enhanced on complexation^{1,2}. Thiosemicarbazones usually react with metallic cation giving complexes in which the ligand behaves as chelating agent bonding through the sulphur and hydrazine nitrogen atoms. Thiosemicarbazones are also used for spectrophotometric determination of metal ion^{3,4}. Thus it is worthwhile to carry out the spectral and structural study of transition metal complexes with such ligands. In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (L^1) and semicarbazone (L^2) (Fig. 1).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All the solvents used were of spectroscopic grade.

Preparation of ligands : Ligands L^1 and L^2 were prepared as reported earlier⁵ by coupling of thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide hydrochloride respectively with pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde.

Synthesis of complexes : A general method had been adopted for the synthesis of the complexes. A hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding metal salts (0.005 mole

Structure of ligands

Y = S, for L^1

Y = O, for L^2

Fig. 1

for each case) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of the respective ligand (0.01 mole) and refluxed for 3-4 h on a water bath. On cooling, a colored complex was separated out in each case. It was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Physical measurements :

The C, H, N was analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the Eleco (CM82T) conducting bridge. Magnetic moment was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a calibrant. Mass spectra were

recorded on JEOL, JMS.DX-303 mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at LNT for Co^{II} complexes and at room temperature for Cu^{II} complexes on E4-EPR spectrometer using DPPH as the *g*-marker.

Results and discussion

Ligand L^1 : In the IR spectrum of ligand L^1 bands corresponding to $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{NH}$ groups appeared at 3370 and 3180 cm^{-1} respectively. The bands corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ groups appeared at 817 and 1590 cm^{-1} . The mass spectrum of free ligand L^1 confirms the proposed formula by showing a peak at 169 amu corresponding to the molecular ion $(\text{M}^+ + 1)\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$. It also shows a peak at 108 amu indicating the loss of

$(-\text{CSNH}_2)$ and various other fragments (Fig. 2).

Ligand L^2 : In the IR spectrum of ligand L^2 bands corresponding to $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{NH}$ groups appeared at 3390 and 3160 cm^{-1} respectively. The band corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ appeared at 1601 cm^{-1} . The mass spectrum of free ligand L^2 confirms the proposed formula by showing a peak at 153 amu corresponding to the molecular ion $(\text{M}^+ + 1)\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}$. It also shows a peak corresponding to loss of $(-\text{CONH}_2)$ at 108 amu and various other fragments (Fig. 3). The mass spectra of complexes confirm the proposed formula by showing a peak corresponding to the molecular ion $(\text{M}^+ + 1)$.

On complexation the bands corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ (in case of thiosemicarbazone) are shifted towards lower side (*ca.* $20\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$). This suggests that the ligand acts as bidentate chelating agent⁶ coordinating through nitrogen of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group and sulphur of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of the ligand L^1 .

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of the ligand L^2 .

group. In case of semicarbazone the bands corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ are shifted towards lower side (ca. 20–30 cm^{-1}) suggest that this ligand also acts as bidentate chelating agent coordinating through nitrogen of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group and oxygen of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ group.

All the complexes provide satisfactory C, H, N and metal analysis which confirm the composition as shown in Table 1. The analytical and physical properties of the prepared complexes are also given in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO corresponds to non electrolytic nature⁷. Thus all the complexes may be formulated as $[\text{M}(\text{L})_2\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} , $\text{L} = \text{L}^1, \text{L}^2$ and $\text{X} = \text{SCN}^-$ and CH_3COO^- . IR spectra of acetate complexes of Cu^{II} display bands corresponding to unidentate nature of acetate group. IR spectra of sulphate complexes of $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Cu^{II} show bands corresponding to unidentate nature of sulphate group. IR spectra of thiocyanate complexes of Ni^{II} show a band around at 2109 cm^{-1} suggesting coordination through S of SCN. IR spectra of the thiocyanate complexes of Co^{II} show a single sharp band around at 2074 cm^{-1} suggesting both thiocyanate groups are nitro-

gen bonded and are in a similar environment^{8–11}.

Magnetic moment values of Cu^{II} complexes at room temperature lie in the range 1.88–2.06 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron. Cu^{II} complexes display electronic spectral bands in the range 11820–15600 and 16000–19550 cm^{-1} . The position of bands suggests that these complexes have tetragonal structure. These bands may be assigned^{12,13} to the following transition in order of increasing energy ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}, {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$.

EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample on X-band at frequency 9.5 GHz under the magnetic field strength 3400 Gauss. All the complexes show anisotropic EPR spectra¹⁴. The g value had also been calculated and given in Table 2¹⁵. $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2) / (g_{\perp} - 2)$, which measures the exchange interaction between copper centers in the polycrystalline solid sample of the complex have also been calculated. According to Hathaway¹⁶ if the value of G is above four then exchange interaction is negligible, if however, the value of G is less than four it indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. In the complexes reported here the value of G is less than 4 indicating the exchange

Table 1. Elemental analysis and molar conductance data of complexes

Complexes	Mol. cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Color	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
					Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{SO}_4$	13	Pink	185–187	66	12.26 (12.00)	29.56 (29.33)	3.49 (3.25)	22.59 (22.81)
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{SCN})_2$	17	Grey	190–193	58	10.64 (10.89)	31.31 (31.05)	2.72 (2.95)	26.12 (25.88)
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{SO}_4$	13	Light purple	237–238	60	12.61 (12.84)	31.59 (31.37)	3.65 (3.48)	24.67 (24.40)
$\text{Co}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{SCN})_2$	12	Ivory	231–233	59	12.08 (12.30)	35.31 (35.07)	3.50 (3.34)	29.48 (29.23)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{SO}_4$	11	Green	195–197	61	11.73 (11.96)	29.57 (29.34)	3.49 (3.26)	22.60 (22.82)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{SCN})_2$	10	Dark green	202–205	65	11.24 (11.49)	32.65 (32.89)	3.37 (3.13)	27.62 (27.41)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{SO}_4$	19	Greenish brown	237–238	60	12.55 (12.79)	31.60 (31.39)	3.23 (3.48)	24.64 (24.41)
$\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{SCN})_2$	15	Purple grey	239–241	60	12.05 (12.26)	35.37 (35.09)	3.09 (3.34)	29.47 (29.24)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	18	Bluish brown	185–187	62	12.08 (12.27)	36.87 (37.09)	4.00 (4.25)	21.40 (21.64)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{SO}_4$	10	Soil brown	194–196	65	12.59 (12.82)	29.30 (29.05)	3.39 (3.22)	22.42 (22.60)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	17	Green	228–230	64	13.32 (13.08)	39.30 (39.54)	4.37 (4.53)	23.35 (23.06)
$\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{SO}_4$	19	Brown	234–236	58	13.52 (13.70)	31.34 (31.06)	3.20 (3.45)	24.39 (24.16)

interaction in solid complexes.

Since sulphato group acts as unidentate, there are two basic configurations with five coordinated geometry i.e. square pyramidal (SP) and trigonal bipyramidal (TBP). The two configurations SP and TBP are characterized by the ground state $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{z^2} respectively. EPR spectra of sulphate complexes provide a very good basis for distinguishing between the two ground states $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{z^2} ¹⁷. For systems with $g_3 > g_2 > g_1$ the ratio of $(g_2 - g_1) / (g_3 - g_2)$, hereafter called the parameter 'R' is very useful for this purpose. If the ground state is predominantly d_{z^2} the value of R is greater than one. On the other hand, for the ground state being predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$, the value of R is less than one. For the present complexes the value of 'R' indicates $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state which suggests a square pyramidal structure.

Magnetic moment values for Ni^{II} complexes lie in the range 2.96–3.25 B.M. Ni^{II} complexes show electronic spectral bands in the range 9600–9990, 14000–15525 and 24380–24850 cm⁻¹ corresponding three spin allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(P) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively which is characteristic to an octahedral geometry.

At room temperature, Co^{II} complexes under study show magnetic moment in the range 4.86–4.95 B.M. corresponding to three unpaired electrons. The electronic spectra of thiocyanate complexes of Co^{II} display electronic spectral bands in the range 9400–10997, 15410–17465 and 19215–25190 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively suggesting a six coordinated octahedral geometry. Sulphate complexes of Co^{II} show three electronic spectral bands around at 13000, 17000 and 25000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to five coordinated square pyramidal geometry. The 4F state of d^7 in an octahedral crystal field is split into three states. Since these states are connected by the spin orbit coupling the spin lattice relaxation times are short making EPR measurements possible only at very low temperature. EPR spectra of the complexes recorded as polycrystalline sample at liquid nitrogen temperature and g values are given in Table 2.

Various ligand field parameters are calculated for the complexes. The value of Dq in Co^{II} complexes were calculated from transition energy ratio diagram using the ν_3/ν_2 ratio¹⁸. The Nephelauxetic parameter β was readily obtained by using the relation $\beta = B(\text{complex})/B(\text{free ion})$, where B free ion for Ni^{II} is 1041 cm⁻¹ and for Co^{II}

Table 2. Ligand field parameters and g value of complexes

Complexes	g	R	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	β	B (cm ⁻¹)
Co(L ¹) ₂ SO ₄	1.97	-	1332	0.96	1103
Co(L ¹) ₂ (SCN) ₂	1.85	-	740	0.51	591
Co(L ²) ₂ SO ₄	1.79	-	611	0.85	971
Co(L ²) ₂ (SCN) ₂	1.86	-	699	0.48	548
Ni(L ¹) ₂ SO ₄	-	-	970	0.71	747
Ni(L ¹) ₂ (SCN) ₂	-	-	960	0.61	638
Ni(L ²) ₂ SO ₄	-	-	975	0.67	703
Ni(L ²) ₂ (SCN) ₂	-	-	999	0.58	614
Cu(L ¹) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	1.99	-	-	-	-
Cu(L ¹) ₂ SO ₄	-	0.126	-	-	-
Cu(L ²) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	1.97	-	-	-	-
Cu(L ²) ₂ SO ₄	-	0.159	-	-	-

is 1120 cm⁻¹¹⁹. The values of β given in Table 2 indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal ligand σ bond.

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